

Ultra-processed food consumption and dietary nutrient profiles associated with obesity: a multi-country study of children and adolescents

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Table S1. Mean (minimum and maximum range) of the dietary contribution of ultra-processed foods (% of total energy) across quintiles of the dietary contribution of ultra-processed foods by country, children age 2 to 5 years, 2004-2014

Country	Mean (min max values) of dietary contribution of ultra-processed foods				
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5
Colombia	0.7 (0 to 3.5)	7.3 (3.5 to 11.2)	15.2 (11.2 to 19.2)	24.5 (19.2 to 30.6)	43.9 (30.6 to 100)
Argentina	3.2 (0 to 9.4)	15.0 (9.4 to 20.7)	25.9 (20.7 to 31.2)	37.5 (31.2 to 43.8)	55.7 (43.9 to 100)
Mexico	8 (0 to 17.7)	24.7 (17.7 to 31.1)	37.3 (31.1 to 43.4)	49.7 (43.4 to 56.2)	69.1 (56.2 to 100)
Chile	18.3 (0 to 27.3)	30.9 (27.4 to 32.9)	41.2 (33.1 to 47.3)	52.8 (47.4 to 57.9)	78.3 (58.2 to 93.3)
Australia	16.6 (0 to 23.5)	29.4 (23.6 to 34.7)	39.8 (34.8 to 45.7)	52.2 (45.7 to 59.4)	70.4 (59.4 to 100)
United Kingdom	39.8 (15.1 to 48.0)	62.9 (48.1 to 57.5)	61.4 (57.5 to 65.0)	69.1 (65.0 to 73.3)	80.1 (73.4 to 98.8)
United States	34.9 (0 to 43.8)	50.2 (43.8 to 54.9)	58.9 (54.9 to 62.8)	67.1 (62.8 to 71.8)	80.0 (71.8 to 100)

Table S2. Mean (minimum and maximum range) of the dietary contribution of ultra-processed foods (% of total energy) across quintiles of the dietary contribution of ultra-processed foods by country, children age 6 to 11 years, 2004-2014

Country	Mean (min max values) of dietary contribution of ultra-processed foods				
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5
Colombia	0.8 (0 to 4.2)	8.5 (4.3 to 12.5)	16.6 (12.5 to 21.1)	26.5 (21.1 to 32.6)	44.9 (32.6 to 100)
Mexico	6.2 (0 to 15.1)	21.9 (15.1 to 27.7)	33.4 (27.7 to 39.2)	45.7 (39.2 to 52.8)	64.9 (52.8 to 100)
Chile	8.9 (0 to 18.7)	25.5 (18.9 to 32.4)	38.5 (32.4 to 45.6)	52.2 (45.7 to 58.4)	66.5 (58.5 to 93.8)
Australia	17.4 (0 to 23.0)	29.5 (23.0 to 34.7)	40.6 (34.7 to 45.7)	53.0 (45.7 to 59.3)	70.4 (59.3 to 100)
United Kingdom	47.9 (18.1 to 55.7)	60.6 (55.7 to 64.4)	67.5 (64.4 to 70.6)	74.1 (70.6 to 77.9)	83.6 (77.9 to 100)
United States	44.7 (5.5 to 53.2)	58.8 (53.3 to 63.3)	66.8 (63.3 to 70.4)	74.6 (70.4 to 79.3)	86.2 (79.3 to 100)

Table S3. Mean (minimum and maximum range) of the dietary contribution of ultra-processed foods (% of total energy) across quintiles of the dietary contribution of ultra-processed foods by country, children age 12 to 19 years, 2004-2014

Country	Mean (min max values) of dietary contribution of ultra-processed foods				
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5
Brazil	1.2 (0 to 5.4)	9.7 (5.4 to 14.2)	19.8 (14.2 to 26.1)	33.7 (26.1 to 42.9)	57.0 (42.9 to 100)
Colombia	0.7 (0 to 3.4)	7.7 (3.4 to 11.9)	15.9 (11.9 to 20.5)	25.9 (20.5 to 32.4)	45.8 (32.4 to 100)
Argentina	2.5 (0 to 8.4)	14.7 (8.4 to 20.8)	26.4 (20.9 to 32.9)	39.5 (32.9 to 47.1)	59.2 (47.1 to 100)
Mexico	6.8 (0 to 15.2)	21.5 (15.2 to 27.6)	33.1 (27.6 to 39.0)	46.0 (39.0 to 53.7)	67.7 (53.7 to 100)
Chile	8.8 (0 to 15.0)	21.1 (15.3 to 27.5)	33.0 (27.5 to 39.1)	45.0 (39.2 to 52.3)	63.9 (52.4 to 97.3)
Australia	16.8 (0 to 23.5)	29.1 (23.5 to 34.8)	40.4 (34.8 to 45.7)	52.8 (45.7 to 59.4)	72.8 (59.4 to 100)
United Kingdom	48.0 (11.8 to 56.4)	61.3 (56.4 to 65.1)	68.6 (65.1 to 72.0)	75.6 (72.0 to 80.0)	85.3 (80.0 to 100)
United States	42.3 (6.2 to 52.7)	58.1 (52.7 to 63.3)	67.3 (63.3 to 71.5)	76.2 (71.5 to 81.0)	88.2 (81.0 to 100)